

Recommended citation: Reid, C., & Dunbar, R. (2018). Communication Skills in Engineering Education: A Fundamental Aspect of Information Processing. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 1151-1158). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672815.

Communication Skills in Engineering Education: A Fundamental Aspect of Information Processing

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Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development, Educational and Organizational Development

Keywords: Communication Skills, Engineering, Information Processing

INTRODUCTION

From an early age, each individual develops a capacity to process information as a result of their biologically primary abilities. Biologically primary abilities are those which an individual is born with, or innate abilities (e.g. information processing and innate communication), while biologically secondary abilities are those which can be acquired and developed through education and training (e.g. engineering language) [1]. As a child matures into adulthood, there is an increase in the complexity of the information that they are presented with, and therefore must process. However, as each individual's development differs, they will not utilise the same methods to process this information. Similarly, individuals will not use the same means of communication.

Communications may be verbal, visual, written, or non-verbal [2] and each of these may be internalised (understood) or externalised (explained). Individuals' capacities to communicate vary significantly. Again, if childhood is taken as an example, each child will begin to talk, draw, paint, write, etc. at different stages of their childhood. As

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that child matures, their skills will advance through the development of various biologically secondary abilities. However, in order for these skills to develop, an individual must be able to internalise and externalise communications effectively to support the processing of information.

Information processing capacity is a vital part of our day-to-day and professional activities. No more so than in the engineering profession. Engineers are often presented with extensive amounts of information and must determine a solution based on the information provided to them. When considering an engineer's capacity to process this information, we must explore how the information is communicated to them and how it comes to be understood. Engineers must understand verbal, visual, written, and non-verbal information that they are presented with and draw meaning from these communications [3].

Information processing is a vital part of this process for engineers. Information processing and communication skills provide an engineer the capacity to understand the complex problems they are presented with. These capacities also provide engineers with a means of expressing their solutions to problems [3][4]. Effective information processing is not possible without effective communication skills, highlighting the importance of biologically primary and secondary abilities operating in tandem in the engineering profession. The relationship between communication skills and information processing is explored throughout this paper and the importance of understanding this relationship for student learning in engineering education.

1 COMMUNICATION SKILLS

An individual's ability to communicate ultimately determines how they progress developmentally. If an individual is lacking in an area of communication e.g. verbal or visual, they may be unable to understand certain other communications or express themselves, therefore hindering their capacity to progress. Understanding the role of the individual in the communication process is central to supporting their development. An individual may internalise (understand) or externalise (explain) the information communicated. The individual's role in communication has also been described as transmitter and receiver through earlier works [5], as illustrated in Figure 1.

Individual's knowledge, skills and abilities develop at different rates due to a number

of such as *Fig. 1. The Shannon-Weaver model of communication [5]* factors,

behavioural, environmental, or personal determinants [6]. While an individual may not be proficient with particular means of communication, they can sometimes compensate with other communications. For example, if an individual is not proficient with written communications, they may compensate with their verbal communication skills. This is sufficient for day-to-day interactions, however, issues may arise throughout their educational experience.

1.1 Communication Skills in Education

Throughout the educational experience, be it early, second-level or third-level education, content is communicated to learners through a variety of means. Internalising communications is a fundamental aspects of learning [7], as well as information processing [8]. An educator may present information visually (e.g. on the board/using models), verbally (e.g. explanation), written means (e.g. notes), or non-verbal (e.g. demonstrations) means [2]. They may also use a combination of these methods of communication to deliver content. However, if a student is not proficient in one of these areas, they may experience difficulty with the education and learning experience, therefore contributing to issues with performance.

The externalisation of communications is an area of particular importance in education in terms of assessment. For example, a person may be extremely intelligent, however, if they are not an effective written communicator they will experience a significant scholastic disadvantage. Similarly, if an individual excels in visual communication, such as sketching, and experiences difficulty with verbal communication, they may struggle if asked to verbally present and explain their visual solution. As noted by Albert Einstein, "Everybody is a genius. But if you judge a fish by its ability to climb a tree it will live its whole life believing that it is stupid". This emphasises the key role that communication skills play in education and assessment.

Communications are a fundamental aspect of all disciplines in third-level education as learners begin to take greater responsibility for their own work. The development of proficiency in communication skills is of particular importance in third-level engineering education programmes as a result of the unique role that communication skills hold in the engineering profession [3][9][10].

1.2 Communication Skills in Engineering

Communication skills are fundamental to the engineering profession as they allow engineers to effectively develop and present their solutions to problems and designs [3][4]. The engineering profession converses in its own unique language consisting of innate communication skills (biologically primary), and engineering communication skills (biologically secondary), for example parametric modelling. This language combines the use of verbal, visual, written, and non-verbal means of communication to describe their solutions to problems to others [2][3][4][11].

For an engineer to effectively understand a problem or a brief, they need to be conversant in all means of engineering communication and have the capacity to internalise this information [2]. This may entail the understanding of technical knowledge, visual representations of information, or verbal descriptions of the brief. If an individual experiences difficulty in internalising these fundamental details, they may encounter problems when developing a solution [4]. Also, if a problem must be solved in a group dynamic, they may experience difficulty in communicating their design to the other members of the group [12], resulting in frustration and a possible lack of motivation to solve the problem.

A range of communications may be used by engineers to externalise their solutions. For example, engineers often use parametric modelling software, working drawings or sketches to visually communicate their solutions [3][11]. Verbal and written communications may also be used to support these visual communications. If an engineer cannot process the communications presented to them, this will contribute to issues with the development of problem and design solutions [2][4], which may have significant practical implications, e.g. structural failure. This highlights the importance of considering information processing capacity in engineering education approaches to support students internalising and externalising communications.

2 INFORMATION PROCESSING

Information processing is the gathering, interpreting and synthesis of information to support decision making [13]. Each individual has a different capacity to store and retrieve information [14]. While some may be highly efficient in processing information, other individuals may experience greater difficulty. As information processing is a biologically primary ability, its capacity cannot be directly developed.

Through cognitive psychology, in order for information to be successfully processed, it requires the combination of memory capacities, which are responsible for the storage and retrieval of information [13][14][15]. Figure 2, presents the Atkinson and Shiffrin structure of the memory system for information processing [16].

Fig. 2. Structure of the memory system [16]

Sensory memory, short-term memory and long-term memory play a fundamental role in information processing [14][16][17]. Sensory memory is the initial stage of the information storage process. The information must be addressed in sensory memory in order to progress to short-term memory [14][16][17]. Short-term memory is also referred to as working memory or conscious memory and is used to understand stimuli and thoughts [14]. In order for this information to be retained, there must be organisation and repetition. The information is ultimately stored in the long-term memory [7][14][16][17]. Throughout the presentation and understanding of information, the collective and synchronous nature of information processing places demands on sensory, short-term, and long-term memory [7][13][14][15][16][17]. The demands that are placed on an individual's memory during this process result in limitations in their capacity to process the information effectively [14][15][17].

2.1 Limitations in Information Processing Capacity

An individual roughly has the capacity to complete two tasks at a time due to the demands placed on the brain to process [17]. When an individual is presented with a number of factors to process, limitations in information processing capacity can occur. There are a number of areas in the brain that cause these limitations.

Sensory memory has a limited capacity to transfer information onto the next stage (short-term memory) for processing and storage, and experiences limitations in a number of ways [14][15][17]. The first limitation is the time it takes for the brain to consciously understand what is seen in visual short-term memory (VSTM), secondly, the restricted capacity of VSTM to hold information, and thirdly, choosing a response [17].

Considering the vast number of decisions that an individual has to make throughout a day, they may experience these limitations on a number of occasions. Regardless, of an individual's profession, there will be significant demands placed on their information processing capacity [13][14][15][17]. However, if we view this in the context of the engineering profession, and the large volumes of information processed when problem solving, it is clear that engineers may frequently experience limitations in processing capacity throughout the problem solving process.

3 THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND INFORMATION PROCESSING IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

Although communication skills and information processing are central to all educational disciplines, their role in engineering education is significant for a number of reasons. Effective innate and acquired communication skills, and information processing are fundamental for engineers to succeed in their key technical roles e.g. understanding and processing complex information, communicating to and with others, and problem solving. This emphasises the need for effective acquired communication skills to be developed throughout engineering education to support the processing of information. Therefore, upon graduation, students will be equipped with the skills necessary to support them in adapting to the changing landscape of the engineering profession as it advances. Efforts now must be placed on a practical approach to developing these core skills within engineering education.

Educational frameworks such as Problem-Based Learning and Project-Based Learning are often implemented in engineering education as they provide students with an applied experience, similar to that experienced in the engineering profession. As problem solving is central to engineering, it is important that students in engineering

education engage in experiences to support the development of problem solving ability. In order for students to acquire the skills necessary for effective problem solving, educators must consider the complexities of the underlying capacities which lead to solutions. Therefore demanding that the relationship between the biologically primary abilities, innate communication and information processing, and biologically secondary, acquired communication skills, is examined and the implications of this relationship on problem solving in engineering.

Communication, information processing and problem solving are each initiated by an external input or information source. Consequently, if one considers that the information an individual stores through processing consists of verbal, visual, written, or non-verbal communications, we can see that communication skills are a fundamental aspect of information processing. When presented with a problem, innate and acquired communication skills, and information processing are necessary to support the identification of key points of the problem so that they may progress to problem exploration. Likewise, throughout problem exploration, solution development, and presentation, communication skills and information processing are utilised continuously throughout the process, as presented in Figure 3.

Capitalising on the natural relationship that exists between communication skills,

Fig. 3. Problem Solving Process

information processing, and problem solving, may scaffold the development of

discipline-specific communication skills within problem- and project-based engineering education approaches. The development of discipline-specific communication skills through engineering education is critical to supporting students in becoming effective communicators and succeeding in their future engineering profession.

4 SUMMARY

It is clear that communication skills, both innate and acquired, and information are central to the engineering problem solving process, and therefore must be considered in the educational approach taken to develop problem solving skills [2][9][10][18]. Much research has highlighted the deficiencies in communication skills of engineering graduates and interventions used to develop these skills [2][18]. However, these skills require continued attention and development as the engineering profession evolves in order to meet societal demands [9][10].

Beyond the engineering profession, communication skills are a fundamental aspect of information processing. To process information an individual requires communication skills, likewise, the understanding of communications requires information processing. This presents the concept that a co-dependent relationship may exist between communication skills and information processing. Should this be the case, there may be significant implications for the acquisition and development of communication skills in engineering and engineering education programs. As engineering curricula seek to achieve an integrated educational and learning experience, the authors suggest that capitalisation on the natural relationship between communication skills, information processing, and problem solving may support the consolidation of knowledge, skills, and abilities in engineering education.

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